

Research Article

Biochemical and structural impact of two novel missense mutations in cystathionine β -synthase gene associated with homocystinuria

Duaa W. Al-Sadeq^{1,2}, Carolina Conter^{3,4}, Angelos Thanassoulas¹, Nader Al-Dewik⁵, Bared Safieh-Garabedian¹, Luis Alfonso Martínez-Cruz⁴, Gheyath K. Nasrallah^{2,6}, Michail Nomikos¹

¹College of Medicine, QU Health, Qatar University, Doha, Qatar; ²Biomedical Research Center, Qatar University, Doha, Qatar; ³Department of Biotechnology, University of Verona, Verona, Italy; ⁴Center for Cooperative Research in Biosciences (CIC bioGUNE), Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Bizkaia Technology Park, Derio, Spain; ⁵Department of Research and Translational and Precision Medicine Research Lab, Women's Wellness and Research Center, Hamad Medical Corporation, and Genomics and Precision Medicine (GPM), College of Health & Life Science (CHLS), Hamad Bin Khalifa University (HBKU), Doha, Qatar; ⁶Department of Biomedical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, QU Health, Qatar University, Doha, Qatar

Correspondence: Michail Nomikos (mnomikos@qu.edu.qa) or Alessandra Astegno (alessandra.astegno@univr.it)

Homocystinuria is a rare disease caused by mutations in the *CBS* gene that results in a deficiency of cystathionine β -synthase (CBS). CBS is an essential pyridoxal 5'-phosphate (PLP)-dependent enzyme in the transsulfuration pathway, responsible for combining serine with homocysteine to produce cystathionine, whose activity is enhanced by the allosteric regulator *S*-adenosylmethionine (SAM). CBS also plays a role in generating hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), a gaseous signaling molecule with diverse regulatory functions within the vascular, nervous, and immune systems. In this study, we present the clinical and biochemical characterization of two novel CBS missense mutations that do not respond to pyridoxine treatment, namely c.689T > A (L230Q) and 215A > T (K72I), identified in a Chinese patient. We observed that the disease-associated K72I genetic variant had no apparent effects on the spectroscopic and catalytic properties of the full-length enzyme. In contrast, the L230Q variant expressed in *Escherichia coli* did not fully retain heme and when compared with the wild-type enzyme, it exhibited more significant impairments in both the canonical cystathionine-synthesis and the alternative H_2S -producing reactions. This reduced activity is consistent with both *in vitro* and *in silico* evidence, which indicates that the L230Q mutation significantly decreases the overall protein's stability, which in turn, may represent the underlying cause of its pathogenicity.

Introduction

Homocystinuria is an autosomal recessive disease characterized by elevated homocysteine levels in the blood, leading to various clinical symptoms. It is primarily caused by a deficiency of the cystathionine β -synthase (CBS) enzyme, which plays a critical role in the remethylation process of homocysteine metabolism [1]. CBS deficiency is caused by a series of genetic mutations in the CBS gene that lead to impaired enzyme function and subsequent accumulation of homocysteine. This build-up can lead to several complications, such as intellectual disability and behavioral disorders [1,2]. Mutations in specific exons of the CBS gene have been linked to the development of homocystinuria [1]. To date, more than 200 pathogenic mutations in the CBS gene have been reported in different ethnic populations [3–9].

Human CBS is a complex pyridoxal 5'-phosphate (PLP)-dependent enzyme with a multifaceted domain architecture that plays a crucial role in homocysteine metabolism, being responsible for combining serine (L-Ser) with homocysteine (L-Hcys) to produce cystathionine (L-Cth). The protein consists of several functional domains, including a N-terminal heme binding domain, a catalytic core domain hosting the PLP, and a C-terminal regulatory domain which is the binding site of the

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allosteric regulator *S*-adenosylmethionine (SAM), a molecule involved in cellular methylation processes. The binding of SAM induces a conformational change in CBS, resulting in increased enzymatic activity [1]. This regulation by SAM is of great physiological significance, as it enables the fine-tuning of CBS activity in response to the cell's metabolic demands and helps maintain L-Hcys levels within a healthy range. CBS not only catalyzes the conventional reaction involved in L-Cth synthesis but also facilitates alternative pathways that produce hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) using cysteine (L-Cys) and/or L-Hcys as substrates. This alternative route for H₂S generation holds substantial biological significance, given that H₂S functions as a gasotransmitter with diverse physiological roles, such as promoting vasodilation, modulating neurotransmission and providing cellular protection [10,11]. The capacity of CBS to drive this alternative reaction underscores its adaptability and emphasizes the intricate interplay between CBS's enzymatic activities in governing L-Hcys metabolism and contributing to various vital processes within the body.

Despite significant advances in our understanding of homocystinuria, the current treatment options remain limited. One common approach is the administration of pyridoxine (vitamin B6 supplements), which can be effective in a subset of individuals with CBS deficiency. However, pyridoxine responsiveness is usually associated with mutations that impair the binding of PLP, a cofactor required for CBS activity. Noteworthy, a significant proportion of homocystinuria patients do not respond to pyridoxine treatment [12]. These individuals are classified as non-responsive to pyridoxine, indicating that their mutations result in more severe enzyme dysfunction or affect metabolic pathways that cannot be corrected by pyridoxine supplementation [13]. Therefore, the pyridoxine non-responsive mutations pose a major challenge in treating homocystinuria, as there are currently no alternative treatment approaches.

Understanding the molecular basis and clinical implications of these mutations is critical to improving the diagnosis, treatment, and care of individuals affected by CBS deficiency and homocystinuria. It has been reported that CBS mutations could lead to disruption of enzyme activity [14]. Patients heterozygous for CBS deficiency may only have elevated plasma homocysteine levels, which can be a risk factor for cardiovascular disease [13]. A recent study reported a patient suffering from severe scoliosis who had elevated total homocysteine levels in plasma and urine [15]. Genetic testing and molecular analysis revealed that this patient was compound heterozygous, carrying two novel CBS mutations c.689T > A, p.Leu230Gln (L230Q) and 215A > T, p.Lys72Ile (K72I). Software for predicting mutation effects reported that these two mutations are located in highly conserved regions [15]. There is currently no research study that characterizes the molecular properties and assesses the pathogenicity of these two missense CBS variants.

Herein, we evaluate for the first time the impact of K72I and L230Q mutations at molecular level by producing the corresponding mutants as recombinant proteins and comparing their biophysical, kinetic and structural properties to those of the CBS^{WT} protein.

Results

Case presentation

The CBS gene is located on chromosome 21q22.3 and consists of 18 exons (Figure 1). The transcription and translation of the CBS gene result in the production of a protein composed of 551 amino acids [16]. The CBS enzyme functions as a tetramer, composed of four CBS protein subunits, and each subunit contributes to the overall enzymatic activity. Since the first mutation in the human CBS gene reported by Kožich and Kraus in 1992 [17], various CBS mutations have been reported in homocystinuria patients from multiple populations worldwide [1].

The present study investigated novel compound heterozygous mutations, c.689T > A (L230Q) and 215A > T (K72I) in a Chinese patient with homocystinuria. Both K72I, located in exon 4, and L230Q, located in exon 8, were reported to be novel as they were not detected in 200 normal control samples. The patient was diagnosed with classical homocystinuria at the age of 18 [15]. The major clinical features of the patient included skeletal abnormality, developmental delays, eye disorders, and vascular events. More specifically, the patient showed Marfanoid habitus with osteoporosis, severe scoliosis, and eye disorders, including ectopia lentis. Significantly increased plasma (268 μmol l⁻¹) and urinary (168 μmol l⁻¹) total homocysteine were observed. Blood methionine elevated to 258 μmol l⁻¹ (normal range 10–50 μmol l⁻¹). Similar clinical features and elevated homocysteine were reported in a Han Chinese family with two novel CBS mutations [14]. The patient was pyridoxine non-responsive, as no significant decrease in the plasma total homocysteine was reported after pyridoxine treatment [15].

Figure 1. Schematic representation of CBS gene and the corresponding protein.

(A) Schematic diagram showing human *CBS* gene, the genomic location of missense variants associated with classical homocystinuria. *CBS* gene is located in chromosome 21q22.3. Variant p.Lys72Ile (K72I) is located on exon 4, and variant p.Leu230Gln (L230Q) is on exon 8. (B) Domain organization of human CBS protein. Human CBS consists of three architectural regions. The N-terminal domain spanning residues 1–70 which binds heme cofactor. A conserved catalytic core, covering residues 70–386, contains the PLP cofactor, where the catalysis occurs. The C-terminal regulatory domain spanning residues 386–551 contains a flexible linker followed by a tandem of CBS domains (CBS1 and CBS2), which form binding clefts for SAM housing.

Molecular modeling and structural comparison of the CBS models

The representative molecular modeling (MD) simulation models for CBS^{WT}, CBS^{K72I} and CBS^{L230Q} were used to explore the structural impact of these mutations at monomeric level. An overlay of these models is shown in Figure 2, and Supplementary Figures SM1 and SM2 from which it can be seen that all variants adopt the same overall folding, with small structural changes that are largely confined to the secondary structure level of the protein architecture. The CBS^{K72I} mutation results in to less extensive conformational changes compared with those of CBS^{L230Q} (RMSD^{WT-K72I} = 5.0 Å and RMSD^{WT-L230Q} = 6.1 Å respectively). These results are in excellent agreement with our circular dichroism (CD) experimental data (see below), where only small structural changes were detected and CBS^{L230Q} had the greater impact.

The catalytic domain of CBS is known to contain a PLP binding site, where PLP as a cofactor is bound primarily by forming a Schiff bond with the ε-amino group of lysine at position 119. PLP is anchored in place by forming a network of hydrogen bonds with residues G256, T257, G258, G259 and T260, located between strands β8 and helix α8. Figure 3A and B show an overlay of the PLP binding site for CBS^{WT} — CBS^{K72I} and CBS^{WT} — CBS^{L230Q}, respectively. The CBS^{K72I} PLP binding site has a similar arrangement to that of CBS^{WT} with most of the changes located on the 256–260 loop (the RMSD^{WT-K72I} for the PLP catalytic site is 2.4 Å). On the other hand, the CBS^{L230Q} is much more distorted (the RMSD^{WT-L230Q} for the PLP catalytic site is 4.7 Å) with key residues adopting a completely different orientation compared with that of CBS^{WT}. These large changes observed at the PLP binding site may result in sterical hindrances that may potentially affect the affinity of the CBS^{L230Q} mutant for the cofactor.

Figure 2. Superimposed MD structures for CBS^{WT} (green ribbons), CBS^{K72I} (blue ribbons) and CBS^{L230Q} (red ribbons). Mutated residues are depicted as space-filling models for reasons of emphasis (red: L230Q, blue: K72I), while the black lines show the location of the cofactor binding sites. Based on the MD results all variants adopt a similar folding. However, CBS^{L230Q} exhibits larger structural changes near the heme binding site.

Another region of interest is the binding site for the heme cofactor, which is located in a hydrophobic pocket formed by residues 40–70 in the N-terminal domain of the protein. When bound, heme is axially coordinated by two amino acid residues, C52 and H65, while additional polar interactions with residues W54, R51, R224 and R266 are also observed. Figure 4 shows the structure of the heme binding pocket in the CBS^{WT}, CBS^{K72I} and CBS^{L230Q} MD structure, while Table 1 summarizes the key properties of the heme binding cavity. CBS^{WT} and CBS^{K72I} form a cavity with similar surface area, although in the case of CBS^{K72I} the pocket is wider, involves more protein residues and is shallower compared with that of CBS^{WT}. As a result, the volume of the CBS^{WT} cavity (270 Å³) is 40% larger compared with that of CBS^{K72I} (192 Å³) but both have the dimensions required to allow heme to enter the binding site. In contrast, the CBS^{L230Q} heme cavity is significantly shrunk, with a total volume of 101 Å³ and only 18 residues involved in pocket formation. The CBS^{L230Q} heme pocket is narrow and does not have the depth necessary to fully accommodate heme, which may reduce the mutant's affinity for the cofactor. This observation also agrees well with our UV-Visible measurements (see below), showing impaired CBS^{L230Q} — heme binding.

GROMACS simulations

To further explore the residual flexibility and stability of the mutated structures, the protein models were subjected to 50 ns MD simulations. The results are collectively shown in Figure 5. Analysis of the 50 ns trajectories revealed a very similar fluctuations pattern for all proteins, with RMSD values increasing rapidly until ~5 ns and stabilized ~1 nm after 10 ns of simulation time (Figure 5A).

The RMSF results of the CBS^{WT} and CBS^{K72I} protein models show nearly identical dynamic fluctuations for all residues, with higher RMSF values corresponding to loop regions or unstructured parts of the proteins as expected (mainly residues 1–50, 450–475 and 510–530). However, CBS^{L230Q} exhibits significantly increased fluctuations for residues 10–40, 381–447, 456–486, 503–508 and 532–551 (Figure 5B), suggesting a less rigid, less stable protein structure for this mutant.

The structural compactness of CBS variants as a function of simulation time can be assessed using the radius of gyration (R_g) of the protein models (Figure 5C). Stable, well-folded conformations typically exhibit small R_g values with minimal fluctuations as the simulation progresses, while unfolded or unstable protein structures show significant fluctuations of R_g during the simulation. Our results show that CBS^{WT} and CBS^{K72I} have a stable R_g of ~2.5 nm after 10 ns, while CBS^{L230Q} has higher R_g values that fluctuate until ~30 ns of simulation time. At that point, CBS^{L230Q} adopts a conformation with a stable R_g which is slightly higher than that of CBS^{WT} and CBS^{K72I}. Similarly to the RMSF results, this can be attributed to a less rigid, less stable structure for CBS^{L230Q}.

Figure 3. MD simulations of CBS^{WT} and mutants.

(A) Overlay of the CBS^{WT} (green) and CBS^{K72I} (blue) PLP binding site, based on the MD simulations structures of this study.

(B) Overlay of the CBS^{WT} (green) and CBS^{L230Q} (red) PLP binding site, based on the MD simulations structures of this study.

Finally, [Figure 5D](#) shows the change of the solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) over simulation time. No significant differences were observed for the CBS variants in this study, with all models stabilizing around SASA values of ~ 250 nm². This indicates minimal changes in the overall protein folding, without co-ordinated exposure to the solvent of the residues that were buried inside the structure at the beginning of the simulation. Overall, the MD simulation results suggest that CBS^{WT} and CBS^{K72I} exhibit similar stability and dynamic behavior, while CBS^{L230Q} adopts a less stable conformation that is significantly more flexible than that of the other two variants.

Spectroscopic features of K72I and L230Q variants

To define the structural and functional effects of the K72I and L230Q substitutions, we expressed, purified and biochemically characterized the CBS^{K72I} and CBS^{L230Q} variants. Both mutant enzymes showed a single main band on the SDS-PAGE gel with molecular mass identical to CBS^{WT} ([Figure 6A](#)). The identity of the recombinant CBS proteins was also confirmed by western blot analysis using an anti-CBS antibody, as previously described ([Figure 6A](#)) [18].

Figure 4. Surface model of the CBS^{WT} (green ribbons), CBS^{K72I} (blue ribbons), and CBS^{L230Q} (red ribbons) heme binding cavity (gray surface), based on the MD simulations structure of the protein.

The basic characteristics of the cavity are summarized in Table 1.

The recombinant CBS^{K72I} enzyme purified to homogeneity was red in color, while the L230Q variant was yellow. Absorption spectra in the UV-Visible region revealed that CBS^{K72I} binds heme similarly to CBS^{WT}, showing a sharp Soret band at 428 nm and a broad absorption envelope for the α/β region with maximal intensity at 553 nm (Figure 6B). On the other hand, by comparing the spectroscopic features of CBS^{WT} in the visible region with those of the L230Q variant, several lines of evidence indicate that the mutation alters the heme binding. First, in the L230Q mutant the absorbance maximum of the Soret peak shows a ~ 10 nm blue shift accompanied by a 3.5-fold decrease in the maximum intensity as compared with the corresponding band of CBS^{WT} (Figure 6B). Second, no detectable bands can be observed in the α/β region in the CBS^{L230Q} spectrum. Thus, spectral data support the hypothesis that the Leu to Gln substitution in position 230 causes impaired heme binding. Far-UV CD spectra of the K72I and L203Q variants were very similar to those of the WT protein (Figure 6C), indicating in all cases a high content of α -helical structure, and that the mutations do not affect the secondary structure of the enzyme.

To acquire information on the effect of the mutations on the stability of the enzyme, the thermostability of the K72I and L203Q variants was measured by CD-monitored thermal unfolding and compared with that of

Table 1. Properties of the CBS^{WT}, CBS^{K72I} and CBS^{L230Q} heme binding pockets, based on the MD simulation structures

Protein	CBS ^{WT}	CBS ^{K72I}	CBS ^{L230Q}
Surface area (Å ²)	276	280	217
Cavity volume (Å ³)	270	192	101
Residues	P46, D47, A48, P49, S50, R51, C52, W54, S61, E62, S63, P64, H65, D221, Q222, Y223, R224, N225, A226, S227, P229, L230, G258, T262, R266, P312, T313, V314, L315, D316, T318, V319	L28, E29, A48, P49, S50, R51, C52, T53, W54, Q55, P59, A60, S61, E62, S63, P64, D221, Q222, Y223, R224, N225, A226, S227, N228, P229, Y233, G258, G259, T260, T262, G263, R266, P312, T313, V314, L315, D316, V319	D47, A48, P49, S50, R51, C52, Q55, R58, R266, E289, I311, P312, T313, L315, D316, R317, T318, V319

Figure 5. Trajectory analysis of CBS variants.

CBS^{WT}, CBS^{K72I}, and CBS^{L230Q} traces are shown as black (—), blue (—), and red (—) lines respectively. (A) RMSD of the protein's backbone atoms, when superimposing the simulated and initial structure as a function of MD simulation time. (B) RMSF graph showing atomic fluctuations of protein residues during simulation. (C) Total radius of gyration (R_g) of the protein's backbone atoms, as a function of MD simulation time. (D) Protein's solvent accessible surface area (SASA) as a function of MD simulation time.

the WT enzyme. These studies were performed by monitoring the decrease in the dichroic signal at 222 nm, which is indicative of the loss of the protein secondary structure, in the temperature range of 15°C–90°C (Figure 6D). All the CD-monitored heating scans reveal that, like the CBS^{WT}, the mutants are denatured in a single-step concerted process. Interestingly, the loss of the secondary structure of the WT and mutant K72I occurs with melting temperatures (T_m) similar to each other ($73.2 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ for the WT and $70.0 \pm 0.4^\circ\text{C}$ for the K72I mutant), while the unfolding of L230Q occurs at significantly lower temperature (T_m $56 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). Thus, the L230Q mutation appears to exert the most destabilizing effect on the protein (Figure 6D).

The thermodynamic stability of the proteins was investigated by chemical denaturation intrinsic fluorescence experiments. Figure 7 shows the chemical denaturation profiles of CBS^{WT} and mutant proteins collected at 25°C. At high concentrations of guanidine hydrochloride, a well-known chaotrope, all variants undergo a reversible two-state unfolding transition with no apparent intermediate state involved. The fitting of a two-state denaturation model to the experimental data can be used to derive the thermodynamic stability parameters for all the proteins of this study. Table 2 summarizes these results and the corresponding standard deviations as determined by the fitting method. Based on the calculated free energy change for the chemically induced unfolding process ($\Delta G_{\text{N-D}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$), the thermodynamic stability of the CBS variants follows the order: L230Q < K72I < WT, as observed for the CD thermal denaturation (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Spectroscopic properties of recombinant CBS variants.

(A) 10% SDS–PAGE analysis of purified recombinant CBS variants and western blotting with a polyclonal CBS antibody (1:1000 dilution). The first lane from left is the molecular marker followed by the CBS WT, K72I, and L230Q samples.

(B) UV–visible absorption spectra of 10 μM purified CBS variants in 20 mM sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.5. (C) Far–UV CD spectra of 0.2 mg ml^{-1} CBS variants in 20 mM sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.5. (D) Thermal denaturation of 0.2 mg ml^{-1} CBS variants recorded following ellipticity signal at 222 nm in sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.5.

Effect of K72I and L230Q mutations on CBS catalytic activity

To explore the potential impact of the K72I and L230Q mutations on the catalytic properties of the CBS enzyme, we analyzed the ability of each variant to catalyze both canonical (L-Ser + L-Hcys) and H_2S -generating alternative (L-Cys + L-Hcys) reactions using reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). While the HPLC profiles of the K72I mutant were superimposable to those of CBS^{WT}, the chromatograms for L230Q exhibited a decrease in the intensity of the L-Cth fluorescence peak. This suggests a lower extent of product formation, indicating that the L230Q variant is likely less efficient at generating L-Cth (Figure 8).

To confirm the functional consequences of our HPLC observations, we determined steady-state enzyme kinetics for both CBS variants in the canonical and alternative H_2S -generating reactions. Table 3 summarizes all the determined parameters, and Figure 9 shows enzyme kinetic assays for CBS^{WT}, CBS^{K72I} and CBS^{L230Q} in the absence and presence of its allosteric activator SAM. The kinetic parameters of the canonical L-Ser + L-Hcys condensation reaction were measured by using a CBL-LDH coupled-coupled assay [19], while those for the L-Cys + L-Hcys condensation were determined using the lead acetate assay [20,21]. Kinetic data obtained for CBS^{WT} were in good agreement with those already reported by other groups [22,23]. The K_m and k_{cat}

Figure 7. Chemical denaturation profiles of WT and mutant CBS proteins, as determined by steady-state fluorescence spectroscopy.

Data are plotted as the weighted average wavelength of the protein fluorescence emission spectra at various guanidinium chloride concentrations ([GuHCl]), after excitation at 280 nm. Solid red lines represent the best fit to a simple two-state model of the form $N \leftrightarrow D$.

values of CBS^{K72I} mutant did not exhibit substantial differences compared with those of CBS^{WT} for both canonical and alternative reactions, suggesting that the K72I mutation does not affect the kinetic properties of the enzyme. On the other hand, the L230Q mutation decreases the k_{cat} value for the canonical reaction by ~4-fold and 7-fold in the absence and presence of SAM, respectively, without affecting the K_{m} values for L-Ser. This results in an overall ~4–6-fold decrease in catalytic efficiency. Interestingly, the effect of the L230Q mutation on the enzyme's ability to catalyze the condensation of L-Cys and L-Hcys yielding H₂S, was even more pronounced. The L230Q mutation led to a small decrease in k_{cat} in the absence (~3-fold) and presence (~4-fold) of SAM. However, this was accompanied by a ~29-fold (without SAM) and 6-fold (with SAM) increase in K_{m} values for L-Cys. Thus, the net result was a dramatic decrease in the overall enzyme catalytic efficiency for H₂S synthesis both in the absence (~84-fold) and presence (~23-fold) of SAM compared with the CBS^{WT}.

Table 2. Thermodynamic stability parameters for all CBS variants as derived by chemical denaturation experiments at 25°C

Protein	$\Delta G_{N-D}^{H_2O}$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	m (kcal mol ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)	$[D]^{50\%}$ (M)
WT	2.41 ± 0.24	-0.76 ± 0.07	3.17 ± 0.12
K72I	2.16 ± 0.15	-0.92 ± 0.06	2.34 ± 0.05
L230Q	2.00 ± 0.17	-1.66 ± 0.13	1.21 ± 0.03

Discussion

In this study, the kinetic and biochemical properties of two novel CBS missense mutations, L230Q and K72I, have been examined. The SNP in exon 4, c.215A > T, results in the replacement of lysine at residue 72 (K72) with isoleucine (I72), and the SNP in exon 8 leads to leucine-glutamine replacement at residue 230. These mutations have been identified in a Chinese patient, who was diagnosed at the age of 18 with classical homocystinuria, characterized by skeletal abnormalities, developmental delays, eye disorders, and vascular events as the major clinical features. Interestingly, the patient with the two pathogenic mutations was unresponsive to vitamin B₆ (a PLP precursor) supplementation as stated by the clinical data. This pathogenic association prompted us to evaluate the biochemical phenotypes associated with the two variants by characterizing the mutant enzymes, obtained as recombinant forms.

The purified CBS^{K72I} mutant exhibited no discernible differences compared with the CBS^{WT} enzyme. UV-visible spectroscopic analysis showed the presence of heme in CBS^{K72I} and steady-state kinetic analysis further confirmed that this variant closely resembles the CBS^{WT} in terms of kinetic parameters. This similarity extends to both its primary CBS activity, involving L-Cth synthesis, and its ability to generate H₂S from L-Hcys and L-Cys as an alternative reaction. Furthermore, the CBS^{K72I} variant exhibited stimulation levels by SAM similar to those of the CBS^{WT}. The minimal impact caused by the K72I mutation on the enzyme's activity and overall stability can be readily explained through its three-dimensional structure. The residue K72 is positioned in an external region of the protein, at the termination point of the heme-binding domain, yet it remains distant from the cofactor. Significantly, its side chain extends towards the solvent and does not engage in any intra- or intermolecular interaction network with other residues that might compromise the functional integrity upon substitution. Therefore, the alternative placement of an isoleucine at this site merely introduces a more localized hydrophobic characteristic, which has no discernible effect on the enzyme's general solubility or its mode of oligomerization.

Figure 8. Analysis of L-Cth production for CBS variants using reverse phase HPLC.

(A) Pure standard L-Ser, L-Hcys and L-Cth (top), and product obtained following a 2 h incubation of CBS single variants with 1 mM L-Ser and 0.8 mM L-Hcys in the presence of 0.5 mM SAM. (B) Pure standard L-Cys, L-Hcys and L-Cth (top) and product obtained following a 2 h incubation of CBS single variants with 1 mM L-Cys and 0.8 mM L-Hcys in the presence of 0.5 mM SAM.

Table 3. Steady-state enzyme kinetic parameters of CBS variants for both the canonical and the alternative H₂S-generating reactions

	Without SAM			With SAM		
	k_{cat} (s ⁻¹)	$K_{\text{m}}(\text{L-Ser})$ (mM)	$k_{\text{cat}}/K_{\text{m}}$ (mM ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	k_{cat} (s ⁻¹)	$K_{\text{m}}(\text{L-Ser})$ (mM)	$k_{\text{cat}}/K_{\text{m}}$ (mM ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
L-Ser + L-Hcys → L-Cth + H ₂ O						
WT	1.7 ± 0.1	7.0 ± 1.1	0.24 ± 0.05	4.7 ± 0.1	3.7 ± 0.3	1.3 ± 0.1
K72I	1.8 ± 0.1	7.2 ± 0.6	0.25 ± 0.03	5.3 ± 0.3	4.9 ± 0.8	1.1 ± 0.2
L230Q	0.44 ± 0.02	7.6 ± 0.7	0.06 ± 0.01	0.67 ± 0.04	3.0 ± 0.8	0.22 ± 0.07
L-Cys + L-Hcys → L-Cth + H ₂ S						
WT	0.91 ± 0.03	0.9 ± 0.2	1.01 ± 0.25	3.3 ± 0.3	4.6 ± 1.4	0.7 ± 0.2
K72I	1.0 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.5	0.63 ± 0.25	2.9 ± 0.4	5.5 ± 2.2	0.5 ± 0.2
L230Q	0.32 ± 0.06	26 ± 8	0.012 ± 0.006	0.8 ± 0.1	26 ± 3	0.030 ± 0.007

Each result shown is the mean ± SE of three ($n = 3$) independent experiments.

Unlike the CBS^{K72I} mutant, the CBS^{L230Q} mutant displays significant deviations from the CBS^{WT} enzyme. Specifically, CBS^{L230Q} exhibits compromised heme binding, reduced stability and enzymatic activity when compared with the native enzyme. The canonical B-type heme found in CBS^{WT}, which is bound axially to the thiolate group of C52 and the imidazole moiety of residue H65, is recognized as a redox sensor able to bind

Figure 9. Enzyme kinetics.

Steady-state enzyme kinetics was performed for CBS^{WT} (A,D), CBS^{K72I} (B,E) and CBS^{L230Q} (C,F) variants in the absence (open circle) and presence (solid circle) of 0.5 mM SAM. Enzyme kinetics for L-Ser + L-Hcys condensation (A–C) was executed using CBL-LDH coupled-coupled assay, while lead assay was used for determining kinetics parameters for the alternative L-Cys + L-Hcys condensation (D–F). Data were fitted using the Michaelis–Menten equation. These kinetic parameters are summarized in Table 3.

exogenous ligands (CO and NO) and to modulate CBS activity, provide structural stability, and enhance protein folding [25]. The interaction between the heme and the PLP active site is thought to result from molecular interactions occurring at both ends of α -helix containing amino acid residues 258–272 (formerly named as either helix- α 8 [26] or helix- α 9 [27] in different articles). Specifically, at the heme end of this helix, residue R266 forms electrostatic interactions with the C52 thiolate, while at the opposite end, T257 and T260 participate in a hydrogen bond network with the PLP phosphate moiety. Functional and spectroscopic investigations on the clinically relevant variants of R266, T257 and T260 have validated the involvement of these residues in conveying information about the heme's redox state and ligand binding to the PLP site [26]. We found that the pathogenic mutant in which the hydrophobic side chain of L230 is substituted for a larger, polar side chain of glutamine residue exhibited a substantial loss of heme content and a significant decrease in overall protein stability and enzyme activity. The L230 residue is situated within 4 Å of the axial ligand. This proximity indicates that the nonpolar amino acid leucine, together with other nearby residues like H67, A226, P229, Y233 or V314, plays a role in maintaining a favorable hydrophobic environment for the heme group. Thus, although the volume of amino acid at that position is one of the factors that affects the heme cavity, we propose a contribution of the hydrophobicity at the 230-position to the control mechanism of the heme binding process. Additionally, similar to the behavior observed for the R266 residue, the reduction in both canonical and alternative activities observed in the L230Q mutant suggests that even subtle structural changes in the heme pocket can be conveyed to the PLP site. Remarkably, the CBS^{L230Q} variant exhibits a more pronounced impairment in alternative H₂S production compared with canonical activity involving the condensation of L-Ser and L-Hcys, a phenomenon previously observed with other mutations [28,29]. In the canonical reaction, we observed no significant differences in the K_m value for L-Ser between the CBS^{L230Q} variant and the CBS^{WT}, but the k_{cat} was ~4-fold lower, resulting in a 4-fold decrease in the mutant's catalytic efficiency. Conversely, in the alternative reaction, substantial differences in K_m for L-Cys were noted, with an ~29-fold increase in the mutant compared with the CBS^{WT} protein, leading to an overall 84-fold decrease in the catalytic efficiency. As suggested for other mutations [28], the distinct impacts of the mutation on two comparable β -elimination reactions may indicate the residue's influence on the leaving group of H₂S versus H₂O, respectively. In addition to the compromised protein stability and heme loss observed in the mutant, the reduced clearance of homocysteine via H₂S synthesis, rather than the conventional reaction, likely plays a role in the accumulation of homocysteine in individuals carrying the L230Q mutation.

The differential effects of the L230Q mutation on the canonical and H₂S synthesis reactions were also observed in the presence of SAM. When compared with CBS^{WT}, the CBS^{L230Q} variant exhibits a roughly 6-fold reduction in catalytic efficiency for the canonical reaction and a substantial ~23-fold reduction for the H₂S synthesis. Interestingly, in the L-Ser + L-Hcys canonical condensation, the decrease in catalytic efficiency is primarily driven by the reduction in the k_{cat} value, as the K_m value for L-Ser remains the same to that of the CBS^{WT}. Conversely, in the H₂S alternative reaction, the overall decrease in catalytic efficiency is influenced by both a significant increase in K_m values for L-Cys and a decrease in k_{cat} .

The finding that the purified CBS^{L230Q} variant cannot achieve the maximum activity level observed in SAM-activated CBS^{WT} supports the importance of retaining heme and its communication with PLP for optimal SAM-responsive activity. This finding offers a possible explanation for the observed impairment in homocysteine metabolism in the patient and underscores the functional significance of SAM regulation of CBS *in vivo*.

Notably, while the expression levels and the yield of the soluble CBS^{L230Q} variant are comparable to those of the WT, and no notable structural changes are evident in terms of secondary structure, (both CBS^{WT} and CBS^{L230Q} proteins exhibit high α -helix content), CD measurements have unveiled a substantial decrease in the thermal stability of the CBS protein due to the L230Q mutation, with a reduction of 15°C. Thus, the mutation of L230 to a polar residue such as a glutamine dramatically affected the overall stability of the protein.

It is worth mentioning that the appearance of a pathogenic profile in heterozygous individuals might be due to the combination of recessive mutations that might result in dominant phenotypes, that are not detected in individuals carrying each single mutation. Establishing whether this is the actual case of the patient described in this manuscript would require further studies. Recent studies demonstrate the enzyme's capacity to form long linear polymeric chains of variable length, composed of dimers, which can adopt two different conformations, basal or activated, in the absence or presence of SAM, respectively. In heterozygous individuals the composition of these chains becomes complicated, as they could potentially include assemblies such as K72I and K72I, K72I and L230Q, or L230Q and L230Q. It is currently unknown whether the intracellular formation of CBS enzyme polymers induces a pathogenic state or if, on the contrary, they represent the natural 'healthy' and active state of the enzyme. The resulting oligomers and polymers from the combination of these dimeric species could

include different percentages of each dimer, depending on the particular conditions and background of each individual. In the absence of further knowledge, it is very difficult to predict, for example, if the different combination of various types of dimers carrying a different mutation in each subunit is the underlying reason for a pathological phenotype, or if any of the combinations of these dimeric species contributes a dominant effect.

Turning our attention to the mutations scrutinized in our manuscript, it is worth noting that the K72I variant, initially presumed to be a polymorphism accompanying the L230Q variant in a Chinese patient, was deemed pathological just on the basis of its location in a highly conserved region of the protein at the sequence level. However, when we have analyzed the three-dimensional structure of the enzyme, it became evident that the presence of an isoleucine instead of a lysine in such a conserved area (in terms of amino acid sequence) does not impact neither the overall enzyme fold, nor its activity or its allosteric regulation by SAM. As mentioned in our manuscript, residue at position 72 points outwards the enzyme, directly to the surrounding solvent, without affecting any intra- or inter-molecular interactions. In line with our prior findings, we have conducted an *in silico* analysis to assess the combined effect of both mutations in complementary polypeptide chains within a dimeric species of hCBS. This analysis encompassed the enzyme's overall folding, the arrangement of critical residues in the catalytic site, and in the heme-binding site. As anticipated, the K72I mutation exhibited no significant differences in all these protein regions compared with the enzyme carrying solely the L230Q mutation. Conversely, the L230Q mutation causes a steric hindrance between the mutated residue and the heme molecule, explaining why this CBS variant does not bind heme and exhibits significantly lower catalytic activity. By extension, these findings strongly suggest that the pathological effect found in the K72I + L230Q heterozygous patient primarily stems from the L230Q variant.

In summary, our comprehensive approach, encompassing computational, spectroscopic, and kinetic analyses, has provided valuable insights into the structural, functional, and kinetic consequences of the K72I and L230Q mutations in CBS. These findings significantly contribute to the expanding knowledge on CBS mutations and their implications in metabolic disorders. All these discoveries not only offer new insights into interpreting the potential impact of specific mutations found in patients but also establish new foundations for developing drugs that can correct and/or regulate the activity and activation of the CBS enzyme in a personalized manner. Furthermore, similar analyses to those presented in this manuscript can aid in understanding how specific mutations affect particular properties of the CBS enzyme, such as its oligomerization mode and conformational changes during allosteric activation, thus paving the way for new translational avenues.

Materials and methods

Molecular dynamics simulations

To investigate the impact of the K72I and L230Q mutations on the CBS structure, molecular dynamics simulations (MD) were performed using the GROMACS 2019.2 software [30,31] along with the GROMOS96 43a1 force field [32]. The structural templates used for the MD simulations were based on structure predicted by AlphaFold for the human CBS protein monomer (Entry P35520) [33]. The CBS variants were created using the mutation tool in Swiss PDB Viewer 4.1 software [34], followed by energy minimization. All proteins were solvated in a cubic box of 10 nm size using the SPC water model and NaCl was added to neutralize the total charge of each system. The resulting models were adjusted using a conjugate gradient algorithm followed by steepest descent minimization with a default tolerance value of 100 kJ mol^{-1} for a maximum of 10 000 steps. All systems were equilibrated at 300 K for 1000 ps using a two-stage ensemble process (NVT and NPT). As a first step, the Berendsen thermostat [35] without pressure coupling was used for the NVT equilibration phase (constant number of particles, volume, and temperature), followed by the Parrinello–Rahman method [36] with a constant pressure of 1 bar (P) for the NPT ensemble (constant particles number, constant pressure, and constant temperature). Finally, the equilibrated system was subjected to 50 ns MD simulation with a time step of 5 fs, using a leap-frog integrator for the time evolution of the trajectories. Clustering of the MD simulation trajectories to select the representative structures used in this study was performed using the gmx cluster analysis tool in GROMACS and the Gromos method [37].

Analysis of molecular dynamics trajectory

The root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) and root-mean square fluctuation (RMSF) were derived from the trajectory files using the g_rmsd and g_rmsf GROMACS tools. The radius of gyration (R_g) and the SASA for each step of the simulation were calculated using the g_gyrate and g_sas commands, respectively.

Variant constructs generation and Sanger sequencing

Human CBS (NCBI Reference Sequence NM_000071.2) was amplified by PCR from pLW2:hCBS. CBS^{WT}, CBS^{K72I}, and CBS^{L230Q} mutants were then cloned in the pET28a vector between NdeI and XhoI restriction sites. We performed Sanger sequencing using Applied Biosystem following the manufacturer's protocol to verify the missense variants in the cloned plasmid. The primers used for the amplification of the K72I constructs were CCACATCATCATACAGCTCCAGCTATATCCCCAAAGATTTTGCCAGACATC (forward) and GATGTCTGGCAAATCTTTGGGGATATAGCTGGAGCTGTATGATGATGTGG (reverse), and for L230Q were GCAACGCCAGCAACCCCCAGGCTCACTACGACACCA (forward) and TGGTGTCTGAGTGTGAGCCTGGGGTTGCTGGCGTTGC (reverse).

Human CBS^{WT}, CBS^{K72I}, and CBS^{L230Q} constructs were transformed in competent *Escherichia coli* (BL21-DE3 Rosetta) cells by heat shock. Cells were cultured at 37°C until the optical density at 600 nm reached 0.6, induced with 0.5 mM isopropyl-β-D-thiogalactopyranoside and grown for 16 h at 24°C. Recombinant CBS variants were then extracted and purified by immobilized metal affinity chromatography using a Ni²⁺-chelating resin, as previously described for the WT protein [38]. The purity of the enzymes was confirmed by SDS-PAGE and western blot analysis using anti-CBS mouse monoclonal antibody (1:1500 dilution; Abnova) as primary antibody and IgG goat anti-mouse (1:2000 dilution-) secondary antibody conjugated with horseradish peroxidase.

Spectroscopic measurements

Absorption spectra were recorded using a Jasco V-750 UV-visible spectrophotometer in 20 mM sodium phosphate pH 7.5. CD measurements were performed on a JASCO J-1500 spectropolarimeter equipped with a Peltier temperature control unit. Far-UV CD spectra of 0.2 mg ml⁻¹ protein samples in 20 mM sodium phosphate pH 7.5 were collected between 190 and 250 nm at a scanning speed of 50 nm min⁻¹ using a 1-mm quartz cuvette (Hellma, Germany) at 25°C. A minimum of three accumulations were made for each scan, averaged, and corrected for the blank solution of corresponding buffer [39,40].

The thermal unfolding profiles of the CBS variants were collected by measuring ellipticity signal at 222 nm in a temperature range between 20°C and 90°C (scan rate 1.5°C min⁻¹) [41,42]. Protein concentration was 0.2 mg ml⁻¹ and measurements were carried out in 20 mM sodium phosphate pH 7.5 buffer using a 1-mm path length cuvettes. The collected data were normalized as fraction of protein population in the unfolded state (fraction unfolded) according to the following equation:

$$f(T) = \frac{CD \text{ signal}(T) - CD^{\text{folded}}}{CD^{\text{unfolded}} - CD^{\text{folded}}}$$

where $f(T)$ and CD signal (T) are the fraction of the unfolded protein population and the measured CD signal at temperature T , respectively, while CD^{folded} and CD^{unfolded} are the CD signals of the fully folded and fully unfolded protein populations, respectively. For a two-state transition, T_m is the temperature at which $f(T_m) = 0.5$.

Chemical denaturation

All steady state fluorescence intensity measurements were performed on using a Horiba Fluoromax 4 spectrofluorometer (HORIBA Advanced Techno, Kyoto, Japan), equipped with a xenon short arc lamp (Ushio). The fluorescence emission spectra of all CBS variants were collected after injecting small aliquots of a dense 8 M guanidinium chloride (GuHCl) solution in a 1-cm path length quartz cuvette (Roth, Germany), containing 0.1 mg ml⁻¹ of protein sample in PBS. Immediately after each addition of GuHCl, the protein concentration was kept constant by adding the appropriate amount of a dense protein solution to the cuvette. The sample was then stirred and incubated at 25°C until a new equilibrium was reached. The spectra were collected between 300 and 450 nm by using an excitation wavelength of 280 nm. The buffer contributions were measured in a separate blank experiment under identical conditions and subtracted from the final data. The titration was carried out until a final GuHCl concentration of 4.5 M was reached. The denaturation profiles are plotted as the weighted average wavelength (λ_{WA}) of the emission spectra at different GuHCl concentrations, based on the equation:

$$\lambda_{WA} = \frac{\sum \lambda_i \cdot I_i}{\sum I_i}$$

where I_i is the intensity of the emission spectrum at λ_i wavelength (300 nm \leq λ_i \leq 450 nm).

Chemical denaturation data were then fitted to a two-state model, describing the induced unfolding as a single transition between the native (*N*) and denatured (*D*) state:

$$\lambda_{WA} = \frac{(a_N + b_N[D]) + (a_D + b_D[D]) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{m_{DN} \cdot ([D] - [D]_{50\%})}{RT}\right)}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{m_{DN} \cdot ([D] - [D]_{50\%})}{RT}\right)}$$

where α_N is the signal of the native state at 0 M denaturant, b_N is the signal slope ($d\alpha_N/d[\text{GuHCl}]$) at the native state, α_D and b_D are the corresponding quantities for the denatured state, m_{DN} is a proportionality constant ($-\partial(\Delta G_{DN})/\partial[\text{GuHCl}]$), and $[D]_{50\%}$ is the denaturant concentration at which the protein is 50% unfolded. The nonlinear least-squares fit of this equation to the experimental data provides an estimate for the parameters $[D]_{50\%}$ and m_{DN} as well as their standard deviations. The free energy change between the native and denatured states (ΔG_{DN}) can then be calculated from the equation:

$$\Delta G_{DN} = m_{DN} \cdot [D]_{50\%}$$

Enzyme activity assays

The canonical activity of CBS variants was assessed using the continuous cystathionine β -lyase (CBL from in *E. coli*) and lactate-dehydrogenase (LDH) coupled-coupled assay as described in [19,43] using a Jasco V750 spectrophotometer in a final volume of 200 μl at 37°C and pH 8.6. The reaction mixture contained 20 μM PLP, 0.2 mM NADH, 1.8 μM LDH, 1.5 μM CBL, 0.1–7 μM CBS variants and 2 mM L-Hcys. The reaction was initiated by the addition of 1–30 mM L-Ser and, subsequently, the oxidation of NADH was monitored at 340 nm.

The production of H_2S was determined following the formation of lead sulfide at $\lambda = 390$ nm ($\epsilon_{390} = 5500 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) as described in [20] at 37°C in presence of 1–30 mM L-Cys and 2 mM L-Hcys. Where indicated, both assays were performed in the presence of 0.5 mM SAM.

High performance liquid chromatography

HPLC analysis was performed using a Jasco LC-4000 HPLC system with a FP-4020 fluorescence detector as reported in [44,45]. The production of L-Cth was analyzed by incubating CBS variants (10 μM) with 1 mM L-Ser (or L-Cys) and 1 mM L-Hcys for 2 h at 37°C in the absence or presence of 0.5 mM SAM. After removal of the enzyme by centrifugation (Vivaspin Turbo centrifugal concentrator, Sartorius), dansyl chloride was added 2:1 to the sample solutions. After a 30-min derivatization reaction at 25°C, 20 μl of the mixture was injected onto a C-18 RP column (Agilent Poroshell 120 HPH RP-C18, 4 μm , 4.6 \times 250 mm). The derivatized products were eluted at a flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} at 40°C with a mobile phase of 33.25/66.75 (v/v) methanol/water containing 0.008% (v/v) triethylamine and 0.6% (v/v) glacial acetic acid. The excitation of the fluorescence detector was set at 335 nm and emission at 522 nm.

Data Availability

The findings of this study are supported by the data within the article and its supplementary materials. Additional information can be obtained by contacting the corresponding authors.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that there are no competing interests associated with the manuscript.

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CRedit Author Contribution

Michail Nomikos: Conceptualization, Resources, Data curation, Formal analysis, Supervision, Validation, Methodology, Writing — original draft, Writing — review and editing. **Duaa Al-Sadeq:** Conceptualization, Resources, Formal analysis, Supervision, Validation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing — original draft, Writing — review and editing. **Carolina Conter:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing — original draft, Writing — review and editing. **Angelos Thanassoulas:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing — review and editing. **Nader Al-Dewik:** Resources, Investigation, Methodology, Writing — review and editing. **Bared Safieh-Garabedian:** Resources, Writing — review and editing. **Luis Alfonso Luis Alfonso Martínez-Cruz:** Formal analysis, Validation, Writing — review and editing. **Gheyath Nasrallah:** Resources, Formal analysis, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Validation, Writing — review and editing. **Alessandra Astegno:** Conceptualization, Resources, Data curation, Formal analysis, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing — original draft, Writing — review and editing.

Abbreviations

CBL, cystathionine β -lyase; CBS, cystathionine β -synthase; CD, circular dichroism; HPLC, high performance liquid chromatography; H₂S, hydrogen sulfide; LDH, lactate-dehydrogenase; MD, molecular dynamics; PLP, pyridoxal 5'-phosphate; RMSD, root-mean-square deviation; RMSF, root-mean square fluctuation; SAM, S-adenosylmethionine; SASA, solvent-accessible surface area.

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Figure S1

Figure S2